

Least squares approximation of ECG signals with rational functions

Software_04: progr1-123.f95

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1. Abstract

This description is closely related to an **older article** of the same main title [1], reading this article will make it easier to understand more. This mainly discusses the working principle of our "**progr1-123**" ECG Feature Extraction program, which is part of our "FEX3 program system".

"This program system **does not extract the features (FEX) automatically**, but with frequent operator interaction."

"A common method is to approximate the signal using a function with parameters that can be set, so that the difference between the signal and the **shapes** of the function (in the biologically relevant parts) is small. Then the parameters of the function that approximate the signal will be considered to be characteristic of it. For this purpose, we have chosen rational functions."

"For the approximation, the rational function was written in the following form (~shape with a root factor)": In the {[1] 4.1. *The approximation function*}. "The program (**progr1-123**) that performs the approximation, ... , in a single step (one run) of approximating 1 wave of 1 period of 1 lead, gradually modifies the initial parameters of the function to minimise the deviation until the stopping criteria are met. In this program (**progr1-123**), the number of parameters does not change."

"Between the steps, he draws the diagram necessary for further decisions, and based on this, the operator determines the next step of the program." The operator will be assisted in this by our programs written in the Octave language [4], which we will also document.

- We explain the structure of the related data files.
- We describe the relationship and operation of related external subroutines.
- For the minimisation, we used the **MINPACK** library downloadable from the Netlib Repository [10]. In more detail: {[1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*}
- During the development of the program, we created a few parts of the program that we didn't use in the end. However, it is possible that we will use these parts again later, so we will briefly write about them. (For example, the decomposition into the sum of partial fractions.) But it's worth reviewing these parts before using them again, because we tested them in a different environment.

This "**2. We repeat...**" section below was copied here verbatim from the description of the "**oneper**" program [9].

Note: In our *.txt files, there are often auxiliary comments at the end of lines used by programs, as well as after lines. (These comments are not used by programs.)

2. We repeat and supplement some information from the mentioned above article [1]:

The **Fortran** we use {[1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*} and its environment:

64 bits processor, Windows 7 Professional with Service Pack 1
GNU Fortran (GCC) 4.8.1 with 0.6.2-mingw32-beta-20131004-1

This compiler is not Fortran IV or Fortran 66: "The GNU Fortran compiler supports the Fortran 77, 90 and 95 standards completely, parts of the Fortran 2003 and Fortran 2008 standards, and several vendor extensions" [3]. In addition to these modern improvements, we can use older subroutines, such as those in MINPACK, without changing the source code!

Our records uploaded in the topic of the main title can be accessed by the following search:

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=creators.name%3A%20%22Kobzos%2C%20Laszlo%22&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>

Since this program system **does not automatically calculate the features** (FEX), but with frequent operator interaction, we create **diagrams** for them, using **MS_EXCEL** or **GNU Octave** [4]. The **transfer of information** between the parts of our program system usually takes place in text files. So are the above programs. In these text files, we used a **decimal point** (for GNU Octave) or a **decimal comma** (for MS_EXCEL). Any text editor can be used to transform them, replacing all commas with points or vice versa.

The source code of our programs is usually provided with many **comments** for their use and possible modifications. The comments are in Hungarian. The same goes for text outputs. We hope that the English language **program descriptions** and **user guides** will be of sufficient help to understand our programs.

We use two types of character encoding:

- For Windows text files and comments: Windows-1250
- For Windows Command Prompt (~DOS) files: OEM 852

If we use Notepad++ : Encoding | Character sets | Central European | ...

The source of the ECG data used { [1] 4.5 *Data* } :

Our ECG data comes from the **PhysioNet database** [2]. From this database, 549 **anonymised** ECG data of 290 individuals can be accessed by selecting PTB. In addition to the signals, the "PTB Diagnostic ECG Database" contains other data, as well (such as: age, sex and diagnosis of the individuals, ...). Signals are sampled at 1 kHz (i.e. 1 sample per 1 millisecond), and a 1mV signal corresponds to a quantisation level of 2000. Although our method is independent of the lead system, we have mainly investigated 3 leads of the **Frank system** (vx, vy and vz; sometimes only x, y and z). Using Dower or inverse-Dower matrix transformations, the data of the conventional 12-lead system can be calculated from the Frank lead system data, and vice versa [5, 6].

The original ECG signals: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.13026/C28C71> License: Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0

We do not deal with cases of **arrhythmia**, because these signs belong to the "should consult a cardiologist" category.

A commonly used method to extract the feature data (FEX, Feature Extraction): "A common method is to approximate the signal using a function with parameters that can be set, so that the difference between the signal and the **shapes** of the function (in the biologically relevant parts) is small. Then the parameters of the function that approximate the signal will be considered to be characteristic of it. For this purpose, we have chosen rational functions." For approximation,

the rational function was written in the root factor form {[1] 4.1. *The approximation function*}. The roots of the denominator and the numerator are called poles and zeros, respectively.

Identifying the periods used { [1] 5. Results, first paragraph }:

The signals tested are denoted as follows: s... = serial number, p... = patient number. For example "s0025_p005". If we want to be more precise about the location within the record, we also indicate the lead and the location of the QRS. For example "s0025_p005, vz, 7009".

The coordinate system used { [1] 4.6. *The coordinate system used* } :

The **x-axis** (t-axis) of a period of a lead was determined with a method usually **used in cardiology**. That is, in the signal-free part before the P wave of the period, we identify a location where the noise is limited, or filter out the noise by "looking", and we mark the starting point of the baseline. The other point of the baseline is similarly determined at the next P wave. The line passing through these two points is called the **baseline**.

The time value of the maximum point of the signal energy (proportional to the square of the voltage) was chosen as the **origin**. This point is always within the QRS-complex. In more detail: In the case of a **Frank lead** system, since it is orthogonal in space, we used the Pythagorean Theorem to determine the curve of the voltage vector length from the vx, vy, vz leads. Its maximum indicates the maximum activity of the electrical signal of the heart. Because of the noise on the leads, we instead cut the curve at 95% of the maximum voltage vector and choose the middle point between the two intersections as the time value of the origin. Since this does not usually coincide with the location of the sampling point, we round to the nearest location.

If we do not use a Frank lead system, but a 12-lead system, then the location of the origin can be determined in the same way using the (nearly perpendicular) V6, II and $-0.5 \times V2$ leads [7].

Addendum to this: In programs, the last character of the variable name is often **A** or **R**. This usually means **Absolute** or **Relative**. For example: i_P1_loc**A**. For the ECG signal downloaded from the database, the character **A** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the signal, while **R** indicates the distance calculated from the starting point of the selected period (P, QRS and T). In those programs that deal with only one period, **A** indicates the distance from the beginning of the period, while **R** indicates the (signed) distance from the QRS wave.

We wrote at the beginning of all our programs written in Fortran (.f95) that we do not use automatic type declaration (**implicit none**). But **usually** the first letter of **INTEGER** variables is "I, J, K, L, M, or N". The **LOGICAL** variables **usually** start with "log_" and **CHARACTER** variables with "ch".

The number of parameters of the above-mentioned function is often listed in programs, data files and diagrams. For example, variable names: ch_fajt12, i_P_fajt1, i_P_fajt2, i_fajt2. For example in figures: P35 "stands for wave P, 3 is the number of parameters of the numerator (including the leading coefficient **d**), while 5 is the number of pole **pairs** (factors) of the denominator. Thus, the number of parameters of the approximation is $3 + 2 \times 5 = 13$."

The two six-character numbers in the data files and in the figures are the timestamp. This 2×6 digit number (yymmdd hhmmss) means "year month day hour minute second".

In our figures containing a single period:

- On the millimeter-scale paper commonly used in ECG machines, the 1×1 mm square of ECG signals (so-called "small square") this corresponds to 40 points

(40 ms)×200 points (0.1 mV) in our drawings. This 40 points×200 points grid - enlarged according to the size of the figure - shown on all our diagrams containing ECG signals.

- Drawing the imaginary values of the roots on the same diagram as the ECG signals we multiplied them by 50, 70, 7 and 50 for the P, QRS, T and Ta waves, respectively (for old ECG signals: 50, 100, 10, -).
- In the figures, the poles are marked with **x** and the zeros with **o**.
- In the figures, only one of the two conjugated complex roots was shown, namely always the one falling towards the momentary value of the signal.

3. Program Description

As described above in section "1. Abstract":

This "FEX3 program system" **does not extract the features (FEX) automatically**, but with frequent operator interaction.

A common method is to approximate the signal using a function with parameters that can be set, so that the difference between the signal and the **shapes** of the function (in the biologically relevant parts) is small. Then the parameters of the function that approximate the signal will be considered to be characteristic of it. For this purpose, we have chosen rational functions.

For the approximation, the rational function was written in the following form (~shape with a root factor): In the {[1] 4.1. *The approximation function*}. The program (**progr1-123**) that performs the approximation, ... , in a single step (one run) of approximating 1 wave of 1 period of 1 lead, gradually modifies the initial parameters of the function to minimise the deviation until the stopping criteria are met. In this program (**progr1-123**), the number of parameters does not change.

At the end of the steps, the program draws the diagrams necessary for further decisions, and based on this, the operator will determine the next step of the program. Of course, the number of parameters may change at this time, usually it will increase, but - for example, in the case of returning to a previous step - a decrease is also possible. The operator will be assisted in this by our programs written in the Octave language [4], which we will also document.

The two main data files of the approximation program (**progr1-123**) are the ECG signal contained in **sam-oneper.txt** {[11] Attachments_files-En.rtf | sam-oneper.txt}, and the coefficients of the approximate rational fraction function (+additional parameters) contained in **adat_file-×_u.txt** (where: × = x, y or z) {[12] | 3.1. - 3.3.}.

3.1. Block structure of parameter file

We will read this file in the "08~ ~~~ chapter" section. We now describe in detail the structure of **adat_file-×_u.txt** (where: × = x, y or z). We will also briefly describe the processing of data blocks. We have already written about them briefly in one of our articles (as much as was necessary there): {[12] 3.1. *Block structure of parameter files*}

This file consists of blocks. We always approximate the next wave using the last block. So, first, in the Ta wave approximation, the file consists of only one block. When the Ta wave is adequately approximated by the function, we insert the P wave block after Ta. Thus, there are now two blocks in the file: the Ta and the P blocks. Since the Ta wave has been properly approximated, the parameter line at the end of the Ta block contain the data of this proper approximation. So the program will approximate this again: the read parameters are less accurate than the double-point parameters stored in the program, but they are very close to it, so the program will perform this current approximation - refinement - in an extremely short time! So now we will only adjust the parameter line of the P wave so that

the "function of P" and the "wave of P" are sufficiently close. The parameters of Ta remain unchanged. Next, we approximate the T wave, so the `adat_file-x_u.txt` file now consists of 3 blocks. Now, we only refine the approximation of the Ta and P waves, and we improve the approximation of T by modifying the T parameter line. The order is: Ta, P, T, QRS.

Note: If there is no Ta wave, i.e. the section between the end of the P wave and the beginning of the Q wave is isoelectric, then the order of the blocks is P, T, QRS.

In the file, the blocks are marked with numbers, this is the wave number: The P, QRS, T, Ta waves are 1, 2, 3, 5 respectively. (The U wave, which we now treat only together with the T wave, would be 6.)

Note: 4 was left out of the program: it was used for a final, joint approximation after each wave was approximated. Unfortunately, if the error decreased for one wave, it increased for another wave. Due to this - no longer used - joint approximation option, we stored all the parameter rows of the approximations in a large array, one after the other. So at the beginning of the array is the P wave parameter line (1), followed directly by the QRS parameter line (2), then T (3), and finally Ta (5). (Of course, 4 was left out here too, because it didn't have a parameter row before.)

The end of the last block is indicated by a line consisting of a single 0 character (block 0).

3.2. Lines of blocks

First line: Wave number of the block.

Second line: For the Ta wave it is always 1. For the other waves (`fajt` line, `fajt12` line): The two hexadecimal numbers are related to the number of parameters of the current approximation. For example: if `fajt12=35` then the number of counter parameters is 3 (including the leading coefficient `d`), while 5 is the number of pole **pairs** (factors) in the denominator $\{[1]$ 4.1. *The approximation function*, 4.2. *Here the notations are as follows*, 4.3. *Properties of the above function form* $\}$.

Third line: The boundaries of the segment to be approximated, i.e. the beginning and end of the waves. The locations here are also in **R** coordinates (relative), i.e. in signed distance relative to the QRS wave.

Fourth line: Weighting of errors. The first two values are the two limits of the weighting locations (R), the third value is the weight value. The weight is naturally positive. If its value is 1.00, then there is nothing to do with it, because the default value of the weight is 1.

The fifth line: See: Fourth line.

The sixth line: See: Fourth line.

The seventh line: The forced 0.0 limits. At both ends of the wave to be approximated, we **temporarily** replace a short section with 0.0. Usually, this part was originally just noise. But of course, it happens that it was a part of another wave of the ECG signal, which we will approximate in another block. To simplify programming, the original signal will be replaced with 0.0 from the first point of the signal to the first limit, and then from the second limits to the last point of the signal. But of course, only the points between the beginning and end of the wave are involved in the calculation of the approximation (see: Third line).

The eighth line: the parameter line $\{ [12]$ 3.2. *Structure of the function parameter line of the parameter file (parameter-line)* $\}$. Note: It is also a programming simplification that the parameter line always has a maximum length and therefore we write 8.88 in the empty spaces. This can be seen in the "AUXX\adat_file-ures.txt" file, where each parameter line still consists of only 0.8880E+01 numbers, which are the numbers 8.88 written in Fortran "E10.4" format. An addition to the description of the structure of the parameter line can be found below in the `{INCLUDE "koz_par.f95"}` section.

Two exceptions:

- The Ta and T blocks contain two more lines before the parameter line. See {[1] 4.8. *Individual waves*}. As we have described in the cited article, a problem with the approximation of Ta can be that Ta usually starts during the P wave and ends during the QRS. In these two sections, we only know the sum of the signals. Fortunately, in these sections, the value of the already small amplitude Ta is even smaller. For more details, see: {09~ ~~~ chapter | Ta wave}.

See: 9~ ~~~ chapter

- The T wave often begins below the QRS complex. In this section, we also only know the sum of these signals. If the T is small at that QRS-T transition, then we will approximate this section of the T wave in a similar way to Ta. As we wrote in {[1] 4.11. *Problems and their practical solutions*}: If we do not find an approximation corresponding to the above rule for a “**dome-like**” T (in the case of a Frank lead, this can also be negative), we classify it in the “needs to be seen by a cardiologist” category, because the “**dom-like**” T belongs there from the start. For more details, see: {13~ ~~~ chapter | Ta wave}.

See: 13~ ~~~ chapter

The two lines above help with these two approximations. For the Ta wave, at the beginning and end. While for the T wave, we can use two auxiliary lines with a breakpoint under the QRS.

Then the contents of two lines are: the location of the two endpoints of a straight segment, and the two (vertical) values of the segment at these locations, and finally the weights of the approximations here.

Input UNITS:

command line parameters: n_xyz: lead number (vx=1, vx=2, vz=3)
log_Oct: True OR False (Oct or Exc = Octave OR Excel)
log_FILT2: True OR False (0 OR 1 number) 99Hz filter2

keyboard: no

101 ECG **sam-oneper.txt** (This is the so-called "vezérlőszalag" = "control tape" out of respect for tradition.)
 {[11] Attachments_files-En.rtf | sam-oneper.txt}
103 parameters **adat_file-×_u.txt** (where: × = x, y or z)
 {[12] 3.1. *Block structure of parameter files*3.1. - 3.2. *Structure of the function parameter line of the parameter file (parameter-line)*}
201 external cycle **ciklus.txt** {[9] 3. **Program Description**}
203 S/N_P/N **AUXX\sorsz_pac.txt** {[9] 3. **Program Description**}
211 **AUXX\adat_fi_STAT-×.txt** **adat_file_mng** subroutine
215 **AUXX\s-ures.txt** **source_mng** subroutine
copy **adat_file-×_u-old.txt** **adat_file_mng** subroutine

Output UNITS:

122 figures (Excel or/and Octave style)
 RAJZOK\rajz-×-00×.txt ×(x,y,z=1,2,3), 00× (1,2,3,4,5)
 RAJZOK\rajz-r-×-rrrrrrrr-00×.txt

RAJZOK\rajz-ru-×-uuuuu-00×.txt

RAJZ_ALL\rajz-×-00×-190809_183516.txt ×(x,y,z =1,2,3), timestamp

RAJZ_ALL\rijz-×-00×-240428_232552.txt (Octave style)

Octa\rajz-rr.txt

Octa\rajz-uu.txt

Octa\VegRajz\rajz-×-00×.txt

124 parameters save **AUXX\param-×.txt** ×(x,y,z =1,2,3), APPEND

126 parameters save (per wave) **rel_par-××.txt** ×(x,y,z =1,2,3), ×(P QRS T _ Ta=1,2,3, _ 5), APPEND

202 statistics **AUXX\stat-×.txt** ×(x,y,z =1,2,3), APPEND

212 **AUXX\adat_fi_STAT-×.txt** **adat_file_mng** subroutine

214 **adat_file-×_u-old.txt** APPEND **adat_file_mng** subroutine

216 **AUXX\s-ures.txt** APPEND **source_mng** subroutine

444 origin,.. **Octa\hely_bazis-nb_pont_.txt**

486 more accurate **Octa\ppaarraamm_×.txt** ×(x,y,z =1,2,3), APPEND

screen: depending on the command line (>NUL)

INCLUDE "koz_par.f95"

nb_point_max maximum number of ECG data

INCLUDE "koz_par_3.f95"

i_P_param_nb i_QRS_param_nb i_T_param_nb maximum number of parameters for the three waves (P, QRS. T)

i_Ta_param_nb i_U_param_nb maximum number of parameters for the two waves (Ta, U)

i6 sum of the previous 5 numbers

The parameters of the period 5 wave are in a single array, in the above order (wave numbers: 1, 2, 3, ×, 5, 6 = P QRS T × Ta U):

the beginnings of each wave in an array can be counted: ik_P_pr, ik_QRS_pr ...

values 1 smaller are more practical for indexing: ix_P_pr, ix_QRS_pr, ...

for example, with the P wave parameters denoted by: {[1] 4.1. The approximation function}:

d c g1 a1 g2 a2... h1 b1 h2 b2...

|-----|-----|

1 1 <-- iPsz (numerator) --><--- iPnv(denominator) ---> 1 + 1 + iPsz + iPnv = i_P_param_nb

then immediately after the QRS similarly.

Mini Hu==>En dictionary:

i	egész	integer
k	kezdet	start
v	vég	end
x	index	index
sz	számláló	numerator
nv	nevező	denominator
nb	darabszám	number
P, QRS, T, Ta, U		wave
Q		QRS wave

After "koz_par.f95", similarly, the ends of the waves follow: iv_P_pr, iv_QRS_pr...

EXTERNAL fcn_4 ! calculates function values (primarily for MINPACK subroutines)

STATEMENT FUNCTION

f_alapv_st_fv(i_form_par) To calculate the points of a line passing through two points (baselines).

01~ ~~~ chapter

For timestamp in character form: **ch_datum**, **ch_tim** (2×6 chars), OR in integer form: **idatum**, **itimi** ($2 \times (3 \times 21)$)

02~ ~~~ chapter

Read the 3 command line parameters. (see above)

03~ ~~~ chapter

We read the "**sam-oneper.txt**" file. {[11], "Attachments_files-En.rtf"}

(This is the so-called "vezérlőszalag" = "control tape" out of respect for tradition.)

We read the number of ECG points: **nb_pont_**.

Then we read in the three leads: the location and value of the starting point of the baselines, then the location and value of the ending point.

Finally, we read **nb_ponts_** times, in order:

The values of the vx vy and vz leads, the 50Hz high-frequency filtered data of the leads, and similarly for the 99Hz filter. But only the filtered data of the selected lead are stored:

na_vez(:,1), **na_vez(:,2)**, **na_vez(:,3)** and **szu1(:,)**, **szu2(:,)**

04~ ~~~ chapter

We calculate the vector length curve and the `location_basis` value. {[9] 07~ ~~~ chapter, 08~ ~~~ chapter}. The length of the vector is normalized to the value taken at location `i_hely_bazis` and then multiplied by 2000 (for later drawing).

05~ ~~~ chapter

In {[9] 02~ ~~~ chapter } we mentioned an outer loop that we no longer use. The value of the cycle variable does not change, its value shows which row of {[8] 13~ ~~~ chapter | qrs_index.txt file} is used, i.e. which period we will approximate. We now read this cycle variable from the "**ciklus.txt**" file into the `i_cycles` variable. (Then we convert it into the `ch3_cycles` character variable.)

Then we write the following 3 values to the file "**Octa\hely_bazis-nb_pont_.txt**": `hely_bazis`, `nb_pont_`, `ch3_cycles`. For example:

```
hely_bazis = 395.00000000000000 ;  
nb_pont_ = 1326 ;  
ch3_cycles = "002";
```

06~ ~~~ chapter

We are not currently using this section. (goto 990).

Since the processing of `vx` `vy` and `vz` together has been completed, it has become possible to read a new control tape (**sam-oneper2.txt**), overwriting the old one. We used this when we examined the approximation of special shapes {[1] 5. Results, fifth paragraph: Then we looked at approximations of some of the more important **shape types**}.

Then we can select any of the 12 leads (up to three) that are **at the same time** as the `vx` `vy` and `vz` leads. It is important to modify the first 13 (1+12) positions of the second "control tape" accordingly. That is, the locations of the baselines should remain the same. However, we need to enter the vertical values of the new leads (at the start and end of the baselines).

07~ ~~~ chapter

We read the value of patient&serial number from the file "**AUXX\sorsz_pac.txt**" into the variable `ch_s_p_name` (for example: `s0038_p007`).

We write out the
separating line,
external cycle `ciklus.txt` data,
patient&serial number,

timestamp

to the "AUX\param- \times .txt" (\times ,y,z=1,2,3), (APPEND) file.

This will be the header for the approximations of the signs written below in the same file.

We write out to the screen (if not redirected: >NUL): external cycle ciklus.txt data, patient&serial number.

In the **yyy(:)** array (sign to be approximated), we enter the data of the corresponding lead (taking into account the baseline of the lead). The values of **yyy(:)** are corrected with the results of the filters, **szu1(:)**, **szu2(:)** :

- We unconditionally correct with the results of the 50Hz filter. (If there was no 50Hz noise filtering, the correction is zero).
- The 99 Hz filtering is done conditionally, depending on the 3rd parameter of the command line (**log_FILT2**).

We open the file **adat_file- \times _u.txt** (where: \times = x, y or z) containing the parameters for later reading.

If there is no Ta wave, it should still have default values (**xx_par(ix_Ta_pr+3)** =0, so its amplitude is 0). We assign values to the variables **i_Ta_fajta**, **xx_par(:)** and **j_wave_Ta**. The entry "**r_lead_coef(5) = 0.0_dp**" is later used by the Octave program part: if it remains 0.0, this indicates that there was no Ta wave.

The default values for the U wave are set in the same way as for the Ta wave. However, since we have not yet encountered a separate U wave, only one that can be approximated together with the T wave, we did not use this part. As we wrote above, program parts that we do not use should be reviewed before using them. In this case, for example, a value assignment is missing (and the array has only 5 elements when declared) "**r_lead_coef(6) = 0**".

By calling the **param_inic** subroutine, we set a few initial parameters of the **lmdif** minimization subroutine { [10] and [1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation* }.

08~ ~~~ chapter

332 CONTINUE **!jwave_Cycle start**.=====>

- We read the wave number (**jwave_**).

If it is 9 (no such wave), then the **adat_file- \times _u.txt** file contains a single special block. In this block, the weights in the part to be approximated are set to 0.0, and the value of the approximating function **d** (the leading coefficient) is and remains 0.0. The goal is to create a starting drawing in which the original ECG signal is properly drawn and the approximating function remains 0.0 throughout. We set the wave number to 3 (T wave), and save the original wave number (9) in the **jwav_sp_** variable (we will use this later to avoid mixing the results with those of the T wave).

If the wave number is 0, we exit the cycle.

GOTO 334 **!Exit from cycle**.=====>

- We read the next line: the **fajt** (fajt1, fajt2) line. For the P wave, we also calculate the number of pairs of zeros in the quadratic numerator, and whether the numerator has a factor of the first-degree. Then the same for the QRS and T waves.
- Third line: The boundaries of the segment to be approximated, i.e. the beginning and end of the waves. The locations here are also in **R** coordinates (relative), i.e. in signed distance relative to the QRS wave. We convert these into **A** coordinates.
- Fourth line: Weighting of errors. The first two values are the two limits of the weighting locations (**R**), the third value is the weight value. The weight is naturally positive. If its value is 1.00, then there is nothing to do with it, because the default value of the weight is 1.
- The fifth line: See: Fourth line.
- The sixth line: See: Fourth line.

The boundaries are placed in the *isuly_forsz_tolig(:)* array. The indexing is: 1,2 3,4 7,8! Also **R** ==> **A**. The values of the weights are set in the *sss(:)* array.

- The seventh line: The forced 0.0 limits. At both ends of the wave to be approximated, we temporarily replace a short section with 0.0. Usually, this part was originally just noise. But of course, it happens that it was a part of another wave of the ECG signal, which we will approximate in another block. To simplify programming, the original signal will be replaced with 0.0 from the first point of the signal to the first limit, and then from the second limits to the last point of the signal. The values remain the same in the other places because the multiplication factor there remains 1.0.

The boundaries are placed in the *isuly_forsz_tolig(:)* array. The indexing is: 5, 6 ! Also **R** ==> **A**. The forcing values are set in the *forsz(:)* array.

We set the logical variables of all waves to FALSE.

Then, according to the waves, "SELECT CASE (*jwave_*)" follows for the approximations of each wave.

09~ ~~~ chapter

The approximations for P, QRS, and T are quite similar. So we will first describe a general approximation. Specifically, this will be the approximation for the QRS wave. For the other approximations, we will only describe the differences.

- *The beginning part:*

The signal to be approximated *yyy(:)* is saved in an array *yym_y(:)*. This way, after any temporary modifications, we can return to the original signal.

We set the *i_par_from* variable to the beginning of the current wave parameters based on the *ik_***_pr* variable in the *koz_par.f95* file (now it is: *ik_QRS_pr*). As we wrote, all parameters of the approximation signal are stored in the *xx_par(:)* array.

We set the variable *i_par_ig* to the end of the current wave parameters, based on the variable *iv_***_pr* found earlier in this description (this is now: *iv_QRS_pr*).

We set the wave's logical variable to TRUE (this is now: *logQRS_*).

We read the parameter line of the block belonging to the wave from the file *adat_file-×_u.txt* (where: × = x, y or z), then write it into the part of the *xx_par(:)* array between *i_par_from* and *i_par_ig*.

The relative (**R**) values of **xx_par(:)** we are converted to absolute (**A**) values using the **ab_srel_iou1b** subroutine.

Then we copy the values of **xx_par(:)** into the **fx_par(:)** array. The values of this array are included in the "temporarily unchanged" values of the approximation function in the external subroutine fcn_4 {[1] 4.7. *Method of approximations*}. Because we usually divide the approximation into "**3 sub-steps of the approximation**".

In fcn_4 **fx_par(:)** name is **fx(:)**, COMMON.

- *The approximation part:*

We have already read the block **fajt (fajt1, fajt2)** line belonging to the wave from the file **adat_file- \times _u.txt** (where: \times = x, y or z). The first value of this is **fajt1** (this is now **i_QRS_fajt1**).

According to its value, we distinguish 3 cases:

- There is only **d** (the leading coefficient) in the numerator. There are only 2 sub-steps here.
- The numerator only has **d** (the leading coefficient) and first-degree factor.
- There is at least 1 quadratic factor in the numerator.

We set the variables **j_step_from** and **j_step_ig** {[1] 4.7. *Method of approximations*} according to the 3 cases.

Note: these 3 cases are not the same as the "**3 sub-steps of the approximation**".

The part **ic_c211013 = 0; ntfev(:) = 0** is not currently used.

We start a cycle with these two limits:

The **j_ $\times\times\times$ _step** (COMMON) variable (this is now **j_QRS \times sw_step**) takes the value of the cycle variable.

We set the value of **mod_par** to the value of the number of parameters of the current wave (this is now **i_QRS_param_nb**).

We call the **lmdif1** subroutine, which will also start the subroutine that performs the approximation (**lmdif**).

The **ic_c211013** and **ntfev(:)** parts are currently not used.

We call the **resz_parm_ki** subroutine with the **j_ $\times\times\times$ _step** variable (this is now **j_QRS \times sw_step**).

This subroutine writes the approximation parameters to the file "**AUX \times \param- \times .txt** (\times (x,y,z =1,2,3), APPEND".

We call the subroutine **resz_rajz_ki**. These drawing data contain the current approximation of the wave. This will help with parameter expansion.

The subroutine creates drawing data in two versions: with decimal comma for EXCEL (**RAJZOK\rajz-r- \times -rrrrrrrrrr- \times .txt**), and with decimal point for Octave (**Octa\rajz-rr.txt**).

- *The ending part:*

In the approximation, it happens that the value of one of the variables **b** in the denominator {[1] 4.1. *The approximation function*} becomes negative. Since we square this, the negative sign disappears, so the sign is irrelevant. But for the sake of clarity, let it be positive. Therefore, we overwrite each variable **b** with its own absolute value.

We put the roots of the quadratic factors of the denominator and numerator (**h** and **g**) in chronological order.

We call the subroutine **ab_srel_iou2b**. This converts the **A** values to relative (**R**). It also writes these values to the file corresponding to the corresponding wave of the corresponding lead: **rel_par- $\times\times$.txt** (\times (x,y,z =1,2,3), \times (P, QRS, T, Ta=1,2,3, 5), APPEND.

Note: The **ab_srel_iou2b** subroutine has another important task. Namely, for the Octave program part, it fills the **rs_sg_sz** $\times(\cdot, \cdot)$ arrays with the values of the poles and zeros, and the **i_sg** \times **nb**(\cdot) array with the number of poles and zeros. First, the value of the leading coefficient **d**, in the next row the standard deviation, in the row after that the number of zeros, then in the next two rows the positions of the zeros, and in the row below it the imaginary values. The quadratic factor containing the two real zeros is split into two, i.e. their values in two places above and two zeros below them, since they have no imaginary part (of course, we also increase the number of zeros by one for this reason). Finally, the number of poles, followed by two rows of poles.

From the saved **yym_y**(\cdot) signal described at the beginning of "*The beginning part*:", we subtract the **ggg**(\cdot) approximation signal, and this is the new **yyy**(\cdot) signal that we want to approximate.

If this signal is still significant, we modify the block corresponding to the wave from the **adat_file**- \times **u.txt** (where: \times = x, y or z) file. Then we run the program again. If this signal is already small for this wave, i.e. just the noise + "small error", then we will approximate a new wave.

The subroutine **resz2_rajz_ki** helps with this. This will draw the new **yyy**(\cdot) waveform. In two versions: decimal comma for EXCEL, and decimal point for Octave.

As we wrote, if the **yyy**(\cdot) waveform is not small enough in the current waveform, we modify the parameter line and then run the program again. During this run, we re-read the original **yyy**(\cdot) ECG signal, and the aforementioned drawing data is overwritten by the program.

At the end of processing **each block** of **adat_file**- \times **u.txt**, the above-described program step "subtract the **ggg**(\cdot) approximation signal from the **yym_y**(\cdot) signal" occurs, so the signal to be approximated becomes smaller and smaller. Finally, after approximating all the waves, only the noise + "small error" remains in the **yyy**(\cdot) array for the entire signal segment.

In the quadratic factors of the numerator {[1] 4.1. *The approximation function*} the storage of the sign of **a** differs from the usual. This is because in the function, this variable appears everywhere only in its square, meaning that whether **a** is positive or negative, its square is always positive. Therefore, instead of the sign of **a**, we store the sign of **a**² here. That is, if the stored sign of **a** is positive, then the sign of **a**² will be positive, if the stored sign of **a** is negative, then the sign of **a**² will be negative. This can be achieved in Fortran as follows: DSIGN(1.0_dp, a) * a**2. One advantage of this storage method is that the sign does not need to be stored separately. The other - more significant - advantage is that during the approximation, the **lmdif** minimization subroutine {[10] and [1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*} **can automatically convert the 2 real roots into 2 imaginary roots, and vice versa, if necessary!**

The **lmdif** subroutine does not use the differential quotient function of the function, but instead approximates it with the quotients of the forward-difference, and for this only the values of the function need to be calculated.

====

Ta wave: As described above in the "*Two exceptions*" section, the approximation of this wave is slightly different from the usual one.

We are writing about the **s_foltoz** subroutine now, because without it the approximation cannot be understood:

First, we read the data of the line: the locations of the beginning and end of the line, then the vertical coordinates at this location, and finally the weighting.

A Ta wave is only present if the signal between the end of the P wave and the beginning of the QRS is not isoelectric, i.e. it is not 0. So the Ta wave (if present) is only known in this short section, not in the sections before and after it. So these are three sections.

The Ta wave starts somewhere after the start of the P wave, this is the start of repolarization. Here its value is 0. Then it continues until the start of the mentioned

short section. This is the first section, this section is approximated by a slanted line (**ter_pol** subroutine), i.e. we temporarily overwrite the real signal, the P wave.

Then comes the second section where we know the sign.

The signal from the end of the second segment - almost symmetrically with the first segment - ceases somewhere below the QRS (third segment). We also approximate this segment with a slanted line, i.e. we temporarily overwrite the real signal, the QRS wave.

Since we do not know the signal on the first and third sections, the weight of the approximation on these two slanted auxiliary lines is preferably less than one, in practice, it is 0.30. Near the 4 breakpoints of the three sections, the value of the weights is reduced by half.

The entire Ta wave is approximated by a 3-parameter function:

$$\begin{array}{c} P3 \\ \text{-----} \\ (t-P1)**2 + P2**2 \end{array}$$

This requires "**2 sub-steps of the approximation**". The first step (*j_wave_Ta* = 4) is the approximation of the main coefficient P3. In the second step, all parameters are changed (*j_wave_Ta* = 1).

The **A R** transformations are now performed by the subroutines **ab_srel_iou1a** and **ab_srel_iou2a**. The latter subroutine fills the *rs_sg_sz* ×(:, :) arrays required for the Octave program part with the values of the poles and zeros. It also fills *i_sg* × *nb*(:) with the number of poles and zeros (the number of zeros is 0). Then it writes this data to the end of the current drawing data (**Octa\rajz-rr.txt** file).

Since there is only one quadratic factor, there is no ordering.

Continued below!

The grid in the drawing corresponds to the usual $1\text{ mm} \times 1\text{ mm}$ size, so the figure has been significantly enlarged.

On the millimeter-scale paper commonly used in ECG machines, the $1 \times 1\text{ mm}$ square of ECG signals (so-called “small square”) this corresponds to 40 points (40 ms) \times 200 points (0.1 mV) in our drawings.

The figures: s0038_p007 7400 vz

In this figure, the two blue lines are important. The line on the left is within the time domain of the P wave. The line on the right is within the time domain of the QRS complex. The middle line is the known signal. You can see that it is not isoelectric, although it is very close to it. (The gray line represents the length of the ECG signals vector.)

In this figure, the green line is the approximation of the Ta wave.

In this figure, the approximate Ta wave has already been subtracted from the original signal. This clearly shows that the P wave is biphasic. The beginning of the QRS wave, or Q, is also more clearly visible than in the original drawing. And the section between the end of the P wave and Q is, to a good approximation, 0.

10~ ~~~ chapter

U wave: not currently used.

11~ ~~~ chapter

P wave. Exactly the same as described for the QRS wave. See: 09~ ~~~ chapter.

We should be prepared for the case where there is no P wave in any of the leads, but we have not encountered such a case among the processed ones so far, so we could not test this. We are not using it at the moment. We skip this experimental part with a goto 777 instruction.

12~ ~~~ chapter

QRS wave. See: 09~ ~~~ chapter.

13~ ~~~ chapter

T wave. Very similar to what is described for the QRS wave. See: 09~ ~~~ chapter.

Differences:

- For the T wave, the leading coefficient and the first-order factor appear in different forms.

This way, convergence is somewhat faster (practical experience).

T wave: $(vlt(1) * ttt + vlt(2))$

P and QRS wave: $(vlt(1) * (ttt - vlt(2)))$

This resulted in minor branches in both the **fcn_4.f95** subroutine and this program (**progr1-123.f95**).

- There is also a difference towards the end of *the ending part*. Namely if **jwave_** wave number 9 (no such wave) see 08~ ~~~ chapter, then the value of **yyy(:)** remains the original, saved signal. That is, **yyy(:) = yym_y(:)**.

- Similar to the Ta wave, it happens with the T wave that we only know the sum of two waves on a section. Namely, the first part of the T wave (since according to signal theory all waves start from zero) begins below the QRS. {[1] 4.8. *Individual waves | T wave*}. For the Ta wave (see: 09~ ~~~ chapter), we have already written about the **s_foltoz** subroutine. We use this here too, but there were parts on both sides of the wave where we only knew the sum of the waves, but here this may only be necessary in the QRS signal part at the beginning of the T wave.

The 4 cases:

-- If the beginning of the T wave begins after the QRS. In this case, the **s_foltoz** subroutine is not needed, the usual approximation methods are used.

-- If the T wave is still small at the end of the QRS. Then we select the estimated starting point of the wave and the point on the T wave at the end of the QRS

and set the weight between these two points to 0.0 (in this case, the auxiliary line is not actually used, only the weight). Then, the points of forced 0.0 values before the estimated starting point of T {see: *08~ ~~~ chapter* | The seventh line} and the part of the T wave after QRS can approximate the empty part below QRS quite well.

-- If, after looking at the approximation of T, we do not consider the approximation to be adequate, we apply what was described for the approximation of the first stage of the Ta wave (an auxiliary line).

-- If this is not suitable, we can try a two-line, broken-line approximation (two auxiliary lines).

Neither method may yield a satisfactory approximation, especially if the T wave is dome-shaped. In this case, repeating the steps described in "[1] 4.11. *Problems and their practical solutions* }":

If we do not find an approximation corresponding to the above rule for a **“dome-like” T** (in the case of a Frank lead, this can also be negative), we classify it in the “needs to be seen by a cardiologist” category, because the "dom-like" T belongs there from the start.

Continued below!

The grid in the drawing corresponds to the usual 1 mm × 1 mm size, so the figure has been significantly enlarged. On the millimeter-scale paper commonly used in ECG machines, the 1×1 mm square of ECG signals (so-called “small square”) this corresponds to 40 points (40 ms)×200 points (0.1 mV) in our drawings.

The figure: s0038_p007 7400 vy

The drawing shows an approximation of the T wave. The black line is the ECG signal. The green line is an approximation of the T wave. The blue thick line (between -46 and -37) drawn by us afterwards (based on the adat_file-y_u.txt) is the signal to be approximated here (forced 0.0). The blue dot at 29 is approximately the QRS boundary. So to the right of this is the known portion of the T wave. To the left of the blue dot, only the sum of the QRS and the T is known, and the weight of the approximation is 0 on this section. Based on the blue thick line and the approximation of the known section of T, it probably adequately approximates the unknown T wave at this section.

14~ ~~~ chapter

If we have not yet reached wave number 0, we go back to the next wave (goto 332).

If we have already reached the wave number 0, we are at line 334 CONTINUE, meaning we have exited the (*jwave_*) approximation cycle.

If any wave approximation is still missing, the program jumps to the "END section" (goto 336). See: 23~ ~~~ chapter.

So at this point, all waves have been approximated, and in the following, we will use the results of the approximations (mainly for data files needed for creating drawings and for collecting results in files).

15~ ~~~ chapter

We looked at the decomposition of approximate functions into partial fractions. We used the *parcialis_1* subroutine for this. But in the end we didn't find it useful, so we "commented out" this part. As usual, if we still want to look at the partial fractions of the functions, we can do so by uncommenting and recompiling the program.

16~ ~~~ chapter

We **recalculate** the entire approximation function with the existing parameters. Partly as a check, partly because this way we calculate the standard deviation of the deviations over the entire signal period. The entire signal period lasts from the beginning of the P wave to the end of the T (possibly U) wave (*i_P_fro_* and **MAX(*i_T_igs, i_U_igs*)**). We recalculate the *yyy(:)* array. We perform the necessary filterings. We set the indices of the starting points of the parameters necessary for calculating all waves at once (offsets: *jjQRS*, ...). Since the P wave parameters are at the beginning of *xx_par(:)*, there is no such offset for the P wave. We set the logical variables of all waves to TRUE. Then we call the subroutine **fcn_4**. The *fff(:)* returned from the subroutine contains the variances (noise + error). Finally, we calculate the standard deviation (*szor_ertk*).

We also use a different standard deviation, the variable *sf_sz210923*. Its value is calculated from the weighted and forced deviations {**3a. Description for fcn_4.f95 subroutine** | 07~ ~~~ chapter | *sf_sz210923*}. The latter is mainly used to evaluate the approximation of individual waves.

Note: the **fcn_4** subroutine is used in several ways:

- Its basic task is to calculate the wave function values for the *lmdif* subroutine (Least Squares Method) that performs the approximation mentioned in the 07~

~~~ chapter.

- It can also be called directly from the **progr1-123 program**. In this case, the *kozy\_bool* logical variable must be set to TRUE. Namely, the **lmdif** subroutine does not return the values of the *ggg(:)* array, which is most important to us, exactly based on the values recorded at the minimum location (but this would not be its task), since **lmdif** still performs new tests in order to achieve a minimum smaller than the previous minimum. Of course, the values of the *fff(:)* and *xx\_par(:)* parameters are exactly the values recorded at the minimum location!

Therefore, if the **lmdif** subroutine we called via the **lmdif1** subroutine (described below), it will also perform a direct **fcn\_4** subroutine call for the exact *ggg(:)* values.

- The third use: calculating the entire function in one step. (Ta, P, QRS, T U). As we wrote above this Note.

Since the parameters start at 1 in the functions (and we organized the cycles based on them), the storage location index here is 0, so there are two different beginnings for each wave (for example: *ik\_P\_pr* and *ix\_P\_pr*).

Finally, we write out the standard deviation to the file **AUXX\param- $\times$ .txt** ( $\times(x,y,z=1,2,3)$ ), APPEND. By calling the **veg\_parm\_ki(1)** subroutine.

17~ ~~~ chapter

We fill the arrays *z\_P(:)*, *z\_Ta(:)*, *z\_QRS(:)* and *z\_T(:)* with the values of the corresponding final approximation functions.

18~ ~~~ chapter

This section discusses the final drawing using EXCEL. The original signal and the approximations are clearly visible. To draw the poles and zeros, we need to set a few things. The poles and zeros arrays initially contain 9 space characters. In the version of EXCEL (we use), we draw short (20 point) helper lines at the beginning of the drawings to indicate the location of the poles and zeros. For the poles of the P wave, it is at a height of 50, for the poles of the next wave, it is at a height of 100, and so on, and then for the zeros similarly. The last line will be at a height of 350 for the zeros of the T wave. By clicking on one of these **lines** in EXCEL, we can set the color, size, and shape of the corresponding **points**.

The location and value of the pole-zero points can be easily determined from the approximation function. For the sake of visibility, the vertical (shape) values were multiplied by a constant value (**pol\_zer\_szorz $\times$** ), for example, for the P wave the plotted value will be 50 times. These values are entered into the pole-zero arrays.

19~ ~~~ chapter

We're creating the header. We've added information to the column names in several places: for example, in columns 4 and 5, the date and time parts of the timestamp. (Here, the names of the partial fractions that are no longer used are also included.)

20~ ~~~ chapter

Since we considered the approximation of each wave to be adequate and prepared the data, the next step is to print the drawing data. We read the original data into the `r_sg444(:)` array. Then we perform the filtering in the usual way. We used a decimal point (for GNU Octave) or a decimal comma (for MS\_EXCEL). Then we print the almost identical drawing in 4 places with the `rajz_wr` subroutine:

An example of the name of the first drawing: `RAJZOK\rajz-z-002.txt`. So the name includes the lead symbol and which of the 5 ECG periods we selected.

An example of the name of the second drawing: `RAJZ_ALL\rajz-x-001-190809_181424.txt`. Here, the previous name has been supplemented with the timestamp data.

An example of the name of the third drawing: `Octa\VegRajz\rajz-y-002.txt`. So the name includes the lead symbol and which of the 5 ECG periods we selected.

An example of the name of the fourth drawing: `RAJZ_ALL\rijz-z-002-250125_204447.txt`. Here, the previous name has been supplemented with the timestamp data.

*Note:* For these last two plots (Octave), the pole-zero data is written at the end of the data file - as for the partial plots. See *08~ ~~~ chapter ab\_srel\_iou2b* for the P, QRS and T waves, and `ab_srel_iou2a` for the Ta wave, in that order.

### *21~ ~~~ chapter*

In this section, we write all parameters and important data in E12.6 format instead of the usual E10.4 precision, at the end of the `Octa\ppaarraamm_*.txt`. The precision can be easily changed because it is set with the `CHARACTER (LEN = 10) :: ch_ppbbfrm = "(1X,E12.6)"` declaration at the beginning of the program.

### *22~ ~~~ chapter*

We write out all the parameters for possible later statistical tests. To do this, we convert the **A** data of the program to **R** data and overwrite them with them, because they will not be needed in the rest of the program (`ab_srel_iou3a` and `ab_srel_iou3b`). We write the parameters, along with some additional data, in a long line at the end of the `AUXX\stat-*.txt` file.

### *23~ ~~~ chapter*

END part.

The program jumps from *14~ ~~~ chapter* to the **336 CONTINUE** instruction if there is still wave that we have not yet approximated.

We print the running time.

If there are new drawings in the `RAJZ_ALL` folder, we set a read only attribute on them.

**End of run.**

24~ ~~~ chapter

Subroutines:

### **lmdif1**

- It minimizes the discrepancy between the ECG signal and the approximating function.
- Before calling, you must set:
  - ***i\_par\_from*** variable: where the parameters of the current wave start in the ***xx\_par(:)*** array.
  - ***mod\_par*** variable, how many parameters belong to this approximation
- Then it calls the **lmdif** subroutine {[10] and [1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*}.
- If the value of any variable in the **lmdif** subroutine is modified, the **param\_inic** subroutine resets it to the initial value (for example, ***nprint***).

### **param\_inic**

- Sets the values of the variables of the **lmdif** subroutine. The ***nprint*** variable is set to 500000. This way, it only prints the values of the parameters of the first and last approximation steps.

### **resz\_rajz\_ki**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *The approximation part*

### **resz2\_rajz\_ki**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *The ending part*

### **resz\_parm\_ki**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *The approximation part*

### **veg\_parm\_ki**

- 16~ ~~~ chapter *Megjegyzés*

### **ab\_srel\_iou1a**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *Ta hullám*

### **ab\_srel\_iou1b**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *The beginning part*

### **ab\_srel\_iou2a**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *Ta hullám*

### **ab\_srel\_iou2b**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *The ending part and Note*

### **ab\_srel\_iou3a**

- 22~ ~~~ chapter

### **ab\_srel\_iou3b**

- 22~ ~~~ chapter

### **root\_sorter**

- The root places are sorted in order. In the numerator, if there are 2 combined real roots, then according to their mean value.

### **rajz\_wr**

- 20~ ~~~ chapter

### **ter\_pol**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *Ta hullám*. Calculates the line that represents the ECG signal in the **s\_foltoz** subroutine. (Line through two points)

### **s\_foltoz**

- 09~ ~~~ chapter *Ta wave* and 13~ ~~~ chapter

### **parcialis\_1**

- Performed the calculation of partial fractions. It is functional, but not currently used.

### **WWW\_1**

- Subroutine for calculating partial fractions (**parcialis\_1**). It is functional, but not currently used. This is the only part of the program where we used complex numbers.

### **lmdif** {[10] and [1] 4.4 *The norm and tools used for approximation*}

- See: **lmdif1**

**adat\_file\_mng**

**source\_mng**

- The **mng.f95** file contains these two subroutines. The subroutines is called by the **veg\_parm\_ki** subroutine.

-- The **adat\_file\_mng** subroutine was mainly used during we development. When the **adat\_file-×\_u.txt** files we changed, this older version is saved to the **ADAT\_FOK** folder.

-- The **source\_mng** subroutine writes the compilation time of **progr1-123.f95** and the modification time of the source code of **progr1-123.f95** and **fcn\_4.f95** to the **AUXX\s-ures.txt** file. Both subroutines can be omitted.

**fcn\_4**

- See **3a. Description for fcn\_4 subroutine** section.

**End of program.**

=====

### **3a. Description for fcn\_4.f95 subroutine**

See: also {**3. Program Description** | *16~ ~~~ chapter* | *Note*}

---

Input UNITS: -

Output UNITS: screen: error messages and information. (Unless >NUL is specified in the command line.)

---

INCLUDE "koz\_par.f95" See: {**3. Program Description** | INCLUDE "koz\_par.f95"}

*01~ ~~~ chapter*

We do not use it at the moment. (GOTO 123). If the approximation took too long, then the **flag.txt** file we saved, and its "Last modification time" is changed. The subroutine notices this with the help of the **STAT** function and exits the **lmdif** program (*iflag* = -1, see: **lmdif.f** comments)

*002~ ~~~ chapter*

This is where the cycle begins. The cycle variable *icc* changes from 1 to m one by one (where m is the number of points of the wave that are currently being approximated).

Cycle start. >=====>

do icc = 1, m

The value of the variable *ttt* is thus the current value from the beginning of the wave to the end. (*m\_eltol* = the place where the wave starts). The variable *r\_sg111* will contain the sum of the values of the (one or more) functions at the time *ttt* at the end of the cycle.

### 03~ ~~~ chapter

The first function calculates the values of the Ta wave. First, the approximation is run with the value of *j\_wave\_Ta* = 4, based on the COMMON variable of the main program. It can be seen that only *vlt(3)* changes, the values of *fx(1)* and *fx(2)* do not change.

*Note:* But, if only one parameter changes, why is the value of *mod\_par* = 3? In older program versions, it turned out that an extremely small reduction in runtime could be achieved by setting the value of *mod\_par* = 1! Moreover, if, for example, in another approximation, two parameters of the approximation function change at the same time, for example the second and seventh parameters, while the others remain unchanged, this would make it very difficult to change the program part. The entire program **progr1-123.f95** still runs in ~1 second. (So, this is not the bottleneck.)

Second, the approximation is run with the value of *j\_wave\_Ta* = 1. At this point, it can be seen that all parameters are elements of the *vlt(:)* array, i.e. they change.

### 04~ ~~~ chapter

The U wave approximation is not currently used (but it is exactly the same as the Ta wave approximation).

### 05~ ~~~ chapter

To approximate the P, QRS and T waves with a function, the **WWW(:,:...)** subroutine is called, with variables specific to the waves.

### 06~ ~~~ chapter

See: {**3. Program Description** | 16~ ~~~ chapter | *Note*}. Here we already have the value of the calculated function in the variable *r\_sg111*.

- If *kozy\_bool* is FALSE, then the weighted and forced values are put into the *fvec(:)* array.
- If it is TRUE, then *ggg(:)* gets its value here, and the *fvec(:)* array is overwritten with the simple differences.

enddo

End of cycle.<===== <

### 07~ ~~~ chapter

The cycle is over, so the **fcn\_4** subroutine has calculated the new *fvec(:)* values of the error function in addition to the changed values of the parameters *vlt(:)* at

each point.

For every integer multiple of the *nprint* variable {3. Program Description | 24~ ~~~ chapter | param\_inic | nprint} in the **lmdif** subroutine call, **lmdif** sets the *iflag* variable of the **fcn\_4** subroutine to 0 (*iflag* = 0, see: **lmdif.f** comments), at which point printing can be done. Currently, the value of *nprint* is 500000, so printing can be done at the initial approximation, the 500000th (*nprint* has never been this high) and the last approximation. We set the value of *nprint* so high because at the moment it is enough for us to monitor the values of the first and last approximations.

In addition to printing the parameters, we also calculate the weighted-forced standard deviation, enter its value into the *sf\_sz210923* COMMON variable and print it to the screen.

Of course, printing only occurs if >NUL is not included in the program command line.

**return**

---

The **WWW** subroutine:

Calculates a point of the rational fraction function selected for approximation in the desired sub-step (05~ ~~~ chapter). The result is returned in the variable *szorz*. It has two main parts: calculating the "NUMERATOR" (SZÁMLÁLÓ) and the "DENOMINATOR" (NEVEZŐ). The parameters of the function in the current "sub-step": variable values are in the *vlt(:)* array, while non-variable values are in the *fx(:)* array. Before the approximation "sub-steps" their value is the same {3. Program Description | 09~ ~~~ chapter | The beginning part}.

*NUMERATOR:*

The calculation of the numerator has a slightly complicated structure: The numerator can be:

- 1. is only of degree 0, i.e. it has only 1 parameter, **d** {[1] 4.1. The approximation function}.
- 2. in addition to **d** there is also a first-degree factor **c**
- 3. there are also second-order factors:
  - 3a. has no first-degree factors (*i\_W\_ef* equal 0)
  - 3b. also has a first-degree factor (*i\_W\_ef* not equal 0)

The structure reflects this. The selection 1. 2. 3. is implemented by a **SELECT CASE ( i\_W\_fajt1 )**.

Choices 3a. and 3b. are implemented by **if ( i\_W\_ef .EQ. 0) then**.

*Notes:*

- in the CASE (3:) form, the colon means: 3 or greater.
- **if ( ix\_W .EQ. ix\_T )** identifies whether we are approximating a wave T. Here the first-degree factor is different.  
{3. Program Description | 13~ ~~~ chapter}
- the 2. and the beginning of 3b. is almost identical (lines 272-290 and 295-313).  
Difference: 301, 302, 303 instead of 201, 202, 203

- the quadratic factors of the numerator have the form  $DSIGN(1.0\_dp, vlt(ic1)) * vlt(ic1)$

{3. Program Description | 09~ ~~~ chapter | The ending part}

*DENOMINATOR:*

Depending on the value of  $j\_W\_step$ , it calculates the value of the denominator:

If its value is 1, 201 or 301, then with the previous  $fx(:)$  parameters {3. Program Description | 09~ ~~~ chapter | The beginning part}. This is the first "sub-step" of the "3 sub-steps of the approximation".

If its value is 2, 202, 302, 203 or 303, then the new variable  $vlt(:)$  with parameters. This is the second and third "sub-step" of the "3 sub-steps of the approximation".

**END subroutine WWW**

## 4. User Guide

We named it **ures.exe** when we linked the compiled program **progr1-123.f95** with the **fcn\_4.o** and **mng.o** object modules.

The preparation of this program can be described very briefly, because all the preparations have already been done by the other programs. There is no need for console input.

## 5. References

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